

Experimental Observations on the Mysterious Explosions from 'Yellow Powder' to enable Yet More Speculation

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Yellow powder (YP) is a simple pyrotechnic mixture that detonates under sustained heating due to an unknown mechanism. While it is possible to speculate of the mechanism behind this explosion, the explanation must naturally align with basic experimental observations. Through simplistic experiments this work shows that the high reliability of the explosion, as well as the capacity to detonate over large compositional changes in the yellow powder dictate that a complex yet consistent mechanism is taking place; one which warrants further study.

Introduction

Yellow powder (YP) is a pyrotechnic mixture of potassium nitrate, sulfur, and potassium carbonate that will reliably detonate upon sustained heating. Early alchemical records of the mixture date back to the mid-1600s,¹ indicating that YP is likely only the second high explosive substance known to human-kind, after fulminating gold.² Despite this long history, the underlying chemistry driving this violent but consistent explosion is still yet to be established.

During live presentations of the reaction, it is often quoted that the reaction is a 'scientific mystery', with this aspect only adding to the appeal of this remarkable demonstration.³ Speculation is common that the detonation may be due to the creation of polysulfides from the basic carbonate and the sulfur, which then from an ideal molecular mixture with the potassium nitrate. While this explanation is plausible, direct experimental evidence to support or reject this theory is lacking.

This work sets out to observe some of the easily quantifiable metrics around the detonation of YP, such as the temperature required for detonation and variations in the cook-off time as the mixture composition

changes. These rudimentary shed observations are conducted in the hope that it will shed some light on the underlying chemical mechanism.

Materials and Equipment

Technical grade reagents were used, with large stockpiles ground to a fine grain size prior to the start of this work, to ensure a consistent particle size was used for each variation in composition throughout this work. Reagents were stored in a vacuum desiccator over calcium chloride to prevent water absorption, particularly from the highly hygroscopic potassium carbonate. Mixtures were generally weighed out in 2 gram batches, thoroughly mixed and stored in the desiccator prior to use. Mixtures were tested within an hour of creation to negate any influence of room temperature reactions between the dry reagents, although no visible reaction was observed in test mixtures stored in the desiccator for a period of several weeks, including no changes in colour or clumping of grains.

Potassium carbonate was acquired as a free-flowing food additive powder and used without further purification. The potassium nitrate was technical grade fertilizer that was

Figure 1 – YP mixture (55/27/18) after extended heating at various temperatures. Each dish was a new fresh mixture, and the picture is taken after 5 minutes of heating with the exception of the 320 °C temperature which was taken after 58 seconds of heating, just prior to its detonation.

purified via recrystallisation from hot water. The elemental sulfur was sold as a soil acidifier and was used without purification, although recrystallisation from hot xylene was once considered.

For heating of the YP, powdered mixtures were loaded unpressed into flat aluminium dishes and placed onto a thick copper plate mounted onto a large electric hotplate. Temperatures reported are the 'hotplate set temperature', which is certainly an overestimation compared to the actual temperature of the mixture.

Results

A YP mixture of 55 KNO₃/27 K₂CO₃/18 Sulfur (by mass) was heated steadily and observed carefully for signs of a violent detonation. This mix (55/27/18) is a reportedly popular composition of YP.⁴ Sustained heating of this YP at 180 °C, 230 °C, 280 °C and 300 °C did not cause any events, however heating at 320 °C caused the characteristic detonation after just over a minute. Further testing observed that heating at 325 °C always caused a detonation, while the same mixture could be indefinitely heated at 300 °C without an event. This then

allows definition of the critical temperature needed for detonation (T_c) as 320 °C.

The YP clearly goes through various reactions at increasingly higher temperatures, shown in Figure 1. At 180 °C the molten sulfur can easily react with the potassium carbonate, forming red polysulfide species. Higher temperatures turn the mixture black, believed to be due to the 'cracking' of the S₈ sulfur rings into linear chains.⁵ Black mixtures return to a red-orange colouration if they are cooled to room temperature before detonation, indicating that the black colouration is from the sulfur, which de-polymerise back into the ring structure on cooling. Mixtures held below the T_c and mixtures held above the T_c appear visually identical until the detonation, as they both let off

The time delay between placing the metal planchette holding the YP on the hotplate, and the mixture detonating (t_d) is of high interest. Figure 2 shows how, for the same dish and heating settings, t_d varies for differing YP amounts. As expected, larger amount of YP in the same geometry of disk have a longer t_d , likely due to the increased reliance on thermal

Figure 2 – The cook-off time, or the required time the YP was heated before it experienced detonation (t_d), slightly increased when more YP was heated at once, without changes to the geometry of the metal dish.

conduction throughout the YP mass to reach the internal T_c needed.

While popular YP mixes are usually 55/27/18 or the closely related 3/2/1 (K nitrate/ K carbonate/sulfur), figure 3 shows that a wide variety of compositions still demonstrate the classic explosive behaviour of YP. Additionally, only slight variations in t_d was seen despite a large change in the composition, with the general trend showing an increase in t_d with higher carbonate mixtures. Surprisingly, given its simplicity, the 1/1/1 mixture was found to be fast detonating and as reliable as the 55/27/18 mixture, showing that even the most

Figure 3 – A ternary diagram showing the t_d of various 400 mg YP compositions, heated on a 325 °C hotplate. The crossed-box markers indicate an event did not occur before 15 minutes of heating time elapsed. The triangle markers indicate the mixture deflagrated but did not detonate.

obvious of YP mixes still produce the desired effect.

Discussion

An explanation of the mechanism responsible for the explosive nature of yellow powder must satisfy the following experimentally derived criteria:

- 1- YP will detonate over an extremely large variation in all components, with only slight changes in the t_d
- 2- YP can be heated above its melting point but below the T_c indefinitely without causing detonation, yet the same mixture will reliably and consistently detonate when heated above the T_c .
- 3- If heated up to/above the T_c point for only a limited time (shorter than t_d) before cooling to room temperature, the resulting frozen mixture is not extraordinarily energetic or impact sensitive compared to unheated YP.

Several theories of the mechanism have been suggested, but it is the author's belief that none of these current speculations adequately satisfy all of these required criteria.

Theory 1: 'Polysulfides are just good fuels'.

This theory is a basic explanation often suggested in online communities attempting to explain yellow powder, in which polysulfides form between from a reaction of the sulfur and the carbonate base which, as a reducing fuel, creates an explosive mix with the molten nitrate oxidiser. This simplistic idea can be dismissed on several fronts. While there is no doubt that polysulfides are created, they clearly form well below the T_c . If the detonation was only due to the creation of reducing/oxidising mixture the continual generation of polysulfides upon heating would make the T_c decrease over time, as mixing and reducing agent levels would increase. This violates Criteria 2. Additionally, the formation of detonation capable ideal mixes over the

wide range of compositional changes is also considered unlikely, against Criteria 1. Finally, the polysulfides that form on heating are still persist at room temperature, such that a frozen room temperature mixture would have the same capacity to detonate as the molten mix under this theory, in contrast to the experimental observations of criteria 3.

Theory 2: Reduction of nitrate to nitrite. Given that there is formation of polysulfides in the mix, and this compound is a reducing agent, it could follow that the molten potassium nitrate is being reduced to nitrite.

Theory 3: Sulfur nitride formation. It has been speculated that S_4N_4 could perhaps form in this mixture due to the presence of nitrogen in the nitrate.⁶ While S_4N_4 and related sulfur nitride molecules are indeed primary explosives,⁷ the formation mechanism from molten nitrate and sulfur compounds seems doubtful and vastly different than its usual synthesis conditions.⁸ The behaviour of the mixture, if it was generating primary explosives, would also likely be different, as tiny amounts of S_4N_4 would be detonating constantly as the mix is held at high temperatures, rather than the whole mix exploding after a consistent delay. Finally, this too is at odds with Criteria 3, as any generated S_4N_4 would have similar primary explosive properties at room temperature compared to above the T_c .

Based on this rudimentary experimental data, several other theories are suggested.

Catastrophic nitrate reduction: When molten, nitrate salts are known to slowly undergo decomposition to nitrite.^{9,10} Although a slow build-up of nitrite salt cannot satisfactorily explain the explosive behaviour, perhaps the mixture suddenly approaches a 'tipping point' in which a large amount of nitrate is suddenly reduced, forming unstable nitrite and heat in such a way that a run-away detonation is

almost instantaneously achieved, especially compared to the time scale of t_d . This could be driven by a physical change in mix, which would satisfy Criteria 1, especially on how t_d is reasonably consistent across mixture composition variations. An example of a physical change driving a sudden catastrophic reduction is the nitrate salt going from suspended particles in the molten sulfur mass to being truly molten/mixing homogeneously with the whole mass. Another speculation could be a rapid change in viscosity in the mixture as it increases in temperature.¹¹ This physical change triggering a rapid switch between a low/zero-nitrate stable mixture and a high-nitrite explosive mixture also satisfies Criteria 2 and 3, assuming that time scale between the physical switch and the detonation is short enough to prevent trapping of the explosive mixture, and the physical switch requires a consistent temperature such that sub- T_c mixtures never reach a high-nitrite state.

Further work looking at substituting the KNO_3 for other alkali nitrates could lend more support for this theory, as one would expect the explosive behaviour to be extremely similar, just with a shifted T_c due to changes in the melting point of the nitrate salt.

It actually is just very good mixing: The mix is extremely viscous and does not generate gas in order to drive mixing of the composition until close to the T_c . The YP is in relatively fine powder before heating, meaning the molten mass is semi-homogeneous once melting first occurs, but true molecular mixing may only be achieved due to the action of the gas generation and the mix detonates once an appropriate mix of fuel and oxidiser is achieved. The t_d is then roughly dictated by the diffusion speed of the ions required for mixing to occur in the molten YP.

This does not easily explain why YP seems unique in its time-delayed explosive behaviour, but perhaps this is a coincidental alignment of a strong oxidiser/strong reducing (generated on heating) mix that also has very slow diffusion due to high viscosity, such that an ordinarily explosive mixture becomes an explosive mixture with a consistent t_d . Alignment of this theory with Criteria 2 is also difficult, although it could be suggested that a slightly sub- T_c mix achieves the same level of mixing (as gas generation also occurs here) but lacks the overall heat to be initiated.

Further simplistic work could look at how the t_d is altered with changes in the initial particle size of the components. Naturally the t_d will change slightly due to changes in the thermal conductivity of the powder, but anomalous results could point in favour of a mixing driven t_d . Perhaps also impact or laser-initiation tests could be conducted on molten sub- T_c mixtures, as the mixing theory implies that this YP has the ability to detonate if only given slightly more energy, in comparison to the other theories which require a new mechanism to take place once T_c is exceeded.

Polymers: The T_c is clearly above the cracking temperature of the S_8 , and then when the mix is returned to room temperature, the S_8 rings reform, the mixture is no longer visually black and the explosive properties are lost. It is possible that there is a correlation between these observations – but it does not explain the role of the carbonate in YP or why S_8 -nitrate salt only mixtures do not share the violent tendencies of YP. But the generation of linear sulfur chains and their associated free-radicals¹² within the YP, perhaps stabilised by the basic carbonate, could be playing a key role in the detonation in such a way that only occurs at the high temperatures needed to crack the sulfur.

Further experiments could be conducted on sodium sulfide-potassium nitrate mixes to see if the YP even requires free sulfur to achieve detonation. Additionally, perhaps there is a reagent that can catalyse the cracking of the sulfur at a lower temperature, and small additions of that may change the T_c of YP, indicating this mechanism.

Conclusion

Modern science is widely believed to have progressed since the 17th century, however, the continued inability of science to conclusively address the significant alchemist mystery of yellow powder brings this belief into question. Advanced analytical machines can only be considered advanced if they are capable of answering long-held questions in ways that would otherwise be impossible, so the existence of solvable-yet-unsolved mysteries challenge the very core of modern science.

It is the author's firm belief that the last 400 years of chemistry research have led us to this; a moment in which we as a society can finally break free of the yellow powder chains that have held us down for so long and step into a golden age of advancement. Surely that is worth the paperwork to bring some explosives into your analytical chemistry laboratory and load it into the most expensive equipment you're allowed to use and just see how it goes? It's what the alchemists would have wanted. Make them proud.

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Supporting Information

Video of the YP explosions, further details of the experimental methods and the author's opinions on certain Australian drug policy decisions can be found at youtube.com/@explosionsAndFire

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